

DIASPORA REMITTANCES AND MACROECONOMIC STABILITY IN NIGERIA AND GHANA (2012–2023): AN EMPIRICAL COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

¹Izuchukwu Ogbodo, PhD, ²Rev. Fr. Christian Akachukwu Ugwuoke and ³Okolie, Jonathan Ibekwe (Ph.D.)

^{1,2}Department of Banking and Finance, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu

³Department of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Esut

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of diaspora remittances on economic growth (GDP growth rate), income levels (GDP per capita), and labour market outcomes (unemployment rate) in Nigeria and Ghana from 2012 to 2023. The study adopts an ex-post facto research design and utilizes annual secondary time-series data sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), Bank of Ghana (BoG), World Bank, International Monetary Fund (IMF), and International Labour Organization (ILO). Data were analysed using descriptive statistics, unit root tests, and Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression to estimate the relationships between diaspora remittances and selected macroeconomic variables in both countries. Empirical results show that diaspora remittances have a positive and statistically significant effect on GDP growth in Nigeria ($\beta = 0.18, p = .04$) and Ghana ($\beta = 0.26, p = .01$). Similarly, remittances significantly increase GDP per capita in Nigeria ($\beta = 28.6, p = .01$) and Ghana ($\beta = 45.3, p = .01$). In addition, remittances have a negative and statistically significant effect on unemployment in Nigeria ($\beta = -0.21, p = .04$) and Ghana ($\beta = -0.13, p = .04$), indicating a reduction in unemployment in both economies, with stronger effects observed in Ghana. The study concludes that diaspora remittances enhance economic growth, improve income levels, and reduce unemployment in both countries. However, Ghana demonstrates more efficient macroeconomic absorption of remittance inflows than Nigeria, suggesting that institutional quality and financial system efficiency determine the extent of their developmental impact.

Keywords: *Diaspora remittances; Economic growth; GDP per capita; Unemployment rate; Nigeria and Ghana*

Introduction

Diaspora remittances, which refer to financial transfers made by individuals living abroad to their home countries, have increasingly been recognized as a vital source of foreign exchange and development financing in many developing economies. These inflows contribute significantly to improving household welfare, promoting economic growth, and supporting macroeconomic stability. According to the World Bank (2023), remittance inflows to Sub-Saharan Africa, including West Africa, reached \$54 billion in 2023. Within this region, Nigeria and Ghana have consistently ranked among the largest recipients, highlighting the importance of remittances to their economic development.

In Nigeria, diaspora remittances constitute a key component of the economy. World Bank (2023) data show that personal remittances amounted to \$20.5 billion in 2023, representing approximately 2.9% of

the country's Gross Domestic Product. These inflows have frequently exceeded foreign direct investment and official development assistance as sources of external finance. The Central Bank of Nigeria underscores their role in stabilizing the naira and cushioning the economy against declining oil revenues (CBN, 2024). Notably, remittance inflows rose by 39% in the first quarter of 2024 (CBN, 2024).

Similarly, Ghana has recorded a steady increase in remittance inflows over time. The World Bank (2023), reports that Ghana received \$4.6 billion in remittances in 2023, equivalent to about 4.3% of its GDP. These funds have been instrumental in supporting household consumption, financing education, and stabilizing the Ghanaian cedi during periods of economic instability (Bank of Ghana, 2023). The continuous growth in remittance inflows reflects their significance in addressing key macroeconomic challenges such as unemployment reduction, poverty alleviation, and overall economic growth.

Despite their growing relevance, the relationship between remittances and key macroeconomic indicators remains inadequately explored. There are still unresolved questions regarding the extent to which remittances contribute to economic growth, improve living standards, and reduce unemployment in recipient countries. In response to this gap, this study examines the impact of diaspora remittances on GDP growth rate, GDP per capita, and unemployment rate in Nigeria and Ghana over the period 2012 to 2023. Although diaspora remittances are widely recognized as an important source of external finance, their impact on key macroeconomic variables such as GDP growth, GDP per capita, and unemployment remains unclear. In Nigeria, remittances have strengthened foreign reserves and supported household consumption, yet their contribution to employment generation is limited, as much of the inflow is used for consumption rather than productive investment (CBN, 2023). A similar pattern exists in Ghana, where remittances help stabilize the cedi and support household spending, but their long-term effects on unemployment and sustained economic growth are still uncertain (BoG, 2023). Existing studies largely emphasize aggregate effects without adequately comparing country-specific impacts or examining interactions with other macroeconomic variables, creating the need for a comparative analysis between Nigeria and Ghana from 2012 to 2023.

The study examines the impact of diaspora remittances on selected macroeconomic variables in Nigeria and Ghana from 2012 to 2023, with a focus on GDP growth, GDP per capita, and unemployment. It seeks to determine how remittances influence these variables in both countries and whether there are significant differences in their effects across Nigeria and Ghana. To guide the analysis, the study tests the null hypothesis that diaspora remittances have no significant positive impact on GDP growth, GDP per capita, and unemployment in the two countries.

This study in the same vein investigates the impact of diaspora remittances on GDP growth rate, GDP per capita, and unemployment rate in Nigeria and Ghana over the period 2012 to 2023. The base year 2012 was selected because it reflects a relatively stable post-2008/2009 global financial crisis period and coincides with improved reliability in remittance data reporting. The period also captures major economic events such as the 2014–2016 oil price crash, the COVID-19 pandemic (2020–2021), and subsequent reforms and recovery policies between 2022 and 2023. Nigeria and Ghana were chosen due

to their prominence as leading remittance recipients, with Nigeria accounting for over 35% of Africa's inflows and Ghana recording high remittances relative to GDP. The 12-year timeframe allows for the analysis of trends, shocks, and patterns using time-series data sourced from the World Bank, IMF, CBN, AfDB, and the Bank of Ghana, focusing only on officially recorded remittance flows. The study is limited to 2023 due to the unavailability of 2024 data.

Despite its rigor, the study faces some limitations. Variations in remittance data across international and national sources may affect accuracy, while an estimated 30% to 50% of remittances in Sub-Saharan Africa occur through informal channels and remain unrecorded. Differences in measurement of macroeconomic indicators, such as changes in Nigeria's unemployment methodology by the National Bureau of Statistics in 2023, also affect

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Diaspora Remittances

Diaspora remittances are financial and non-financial resources transferred by migrants to their home countries, typically through formal channels such as banks, money transfer operators, and fintech platforms. The World Bank (2023) defines them as cross-border personal monetary transfers from migrant workers. Globally, remittances have grown significantly, often surpassing foreign direct investment (FDI) in low- and middle-income countries, and serving as a vital source of income for households by supporting education, healthcare, housing, and general welfare.

In Sub-Saharan Africa, remittances play a major developmental role. In Ghana, inflows increased from \$2.5 billion in 2012 to \$4.6 billion in 2023, contributing about 6% of GDP and strengthening foreign reserves (Bank of Ghana, 2023). In Nigeria, remittances consistently exceeded \$20 billion annually over the same period, making it the largest recipient in the region and one of the top 10 globally (CBN, 2023). While formal channels dominate, a significant share, estimated at 30% to 50%, flows through informal means due to high transaction costs and exchange rate constraints (World Bank, 2023).

Beyond financial flows, remittances also include social transfers such as knowledge, skills, and cultural practices that contribute to innovation and social development.

Nigeria and Ghana in Context

In both Nigeria and Ghana, remittances are critical for economic stability. In Ghana, they support the cedi, finance imports, and reduce reliance on external borrowing, while also funding household needs and small-scale investments (Bank of Ghana, 2023). In Nigeria, remittances help stabilize the naira, especially during oil price shocks, such as the 2016 oil crisis, and serve as a reliable source of foreign exchange (CBN, 2023).

Across both countries, remittances contribute to financing development projects, reducing poverty, stabilizing exchange rates, and promoting financial inclusion. However, challenges remain, including policy and exchange rate distortions in Nigeria that encourage informal transfers, and high transaction costs in Ghana averaging 8–9% per \$200 transfer compared to the global average of 6% (World Bank, 2022)

Macroeconomic Variables

Macroeconomic variables are broad indicators used to assess the overall performance of an economy, similar to how vital signs reflect a person's health. A key measure is Gross Domestic Product (GDP), which represents the total value of goods and services produced; rising GDP indicates economic expansion and improved income and employment opportunities (World Bank, 2022).

In this study, three core indicators are used to evaluate the impact of diaspora remittances. The GDP growth rate measures the annual percentage increase in economic output and reflects overall economic expansion, which remittances can stimulate through increased consumption and investment. GDP per capita captures average income per person and living standards, with remittances contributing by raising household income, particularly in countries like Nigeria and Ghana. The unemployment rate represents the share of the labour force without jobs, and although remittances do not directly create employment, they can indirectly reduce unemployment by supporting small businesses, education, and skill development.

These variables are selected because they collectively capture economic growth, living standards, and employment conditions. Remittances influence them by boosting household income, encouraging consumption, supporting investments, and enhancing financial stability, thereby providing a comprehensive basis for assessing their impact on economic development in Nigeria, Ghana, and similar developing economies

Theoretical Review

The impact of diaspora remittances on macroeconomic variables is grounded in several key economic theories that collectively explain their influence on growth, employment, investment, and income distribution. The Keynesian Theory of Income and Employment 1936, argues that increases in aggregate demand lead to higher national income and employment. In this context, diaspora remittances raise household disposable income, which increases consumption of goods and services. This stimulates demand in the economy, prompting producers to expand output and hire more labour, thereby contributing to economic growth in countries such as Nigeria and Ghana.

The Neoclassical Growth Theory advanced by Solow in 1956 emphasizes capital accumulation, technological progress, and labour force expansion as drivers of long-term economic growth. Remittances serve as an important form of capital inflow, especially in developing economies with weak financial systems. In Nigeria and Ghana, these funds are often invested in education, healthcare, housing, agriculture, and small-scale enterprises, leading to higher productivity and sustained output growth.

The Migration and Development Theory by the modern proponentde Haas 2005, further explains that migration and remittances are not only financial flows but also channels for transferring skills, knowledge, and social capital. In both Nigeria and Ghana, remittances contribute to poverty reduction, social transformation, and economic diversification, while also supporting community development projects such as schools, healthcare facilities, and infrastructure initiatives funded by diaspora groups.

The Endogenous Growth Theory championed by Romer, 1986; Lucas, 1990s, highlights the role of human capital, innovation, and knowledge accumulation in driving long-term growth. Remittances support investments in education, vocational training, healthcare, and entrepreneurship, thereby strengthening human capital and productivity. In Nigeria and Ghana, such investments enhance innovation capacity and contribute to sustained economic development.

These theories, collectively point to the fact that diaspora remittances influence economic performance through increased consumption, capital formation, human capital development, and broader structural transformation in developing economies.

Empirical Review

The following empirical studies were reviewed and presented with insightful evidence on the relationship between diaspora remittances and macroeconomic outcomes such as GDP growth, poverty reduction, financial development, and economic stability across countries.

Chami et al. (2005), using global panel data and regressions, found that remittances do not consistently promote GDP growth and may reduce labour force participation, suggesting possible negative incentive effects. In contrast, Anyanwu and Erhijakpor (2010), using OLS on 33 African countries, found that remittances significantly reduce poverty and improve household welfare.

Akonji and Wakili (2013) applied ECM techniques and found that remittances positively affect GDP in both the short and long run, while Nwagu and Amedu (2011) similarly reported a positive impact on GDP per capita using ARDL. However, Kudaisi et al. (2022), using System-GMM, found a negative long-run effect of remittances on GDP, suggesting possible non-productive use of inflows.

Oteng-Abayie et al. (2020) and Oteng-Abayie (2020), using PMG-ARDL and ARDL models, found short-run positive effects but potential long-run negative effects of remittances on GDP growth, highlighting possible dependency and Dutch-disease effects. In contrast, Sasu (2022), using household survey data, showed that remittances mainly improve welfare through consumption smoothing rather than directly boosting GDP.

Adams and Klobodu (2016) found that remittances positively affect growth in Sub-Saharan Africa, especially in countries with strong institutions, while Sobiech (2015) reported negative growth effects where institutions are weak. Similarly, Olayungbo and Quadri (2019), using PMG-ARDL, confirmed positive long-run effects of remittances in SSA, conditional on financial development.

Cooray (2012) found that remittances promote growth more strongly in financially open economies, while Gazdar and Kratou (2012) showed that remittances complement financial development by supporting savings and credit expansion. Likewise, Falade et al. (2021) and Kibet and Agbelenko (2015) confirmed that remittances enhance financial deepening when supported by strong banking systems.

Cunningham et al. (2019) found that remittances improve resilience to external shocks, while Bouoiyour et al. (2017) showed they act as stabilizers during political instability. Karikari et al. (2016) further emphasized that remittances affect growth indirectly through financial inclusion and credit channels rather than directly.

Bank of Ghana (2023) and Central Bank of Nigeria (2023) confirms that remittances significantly support foreign exchange stability, financial inclusion, and household consumption, contributing up to 5–6% of GDP in Nigeria. The World Bank (2023) also highlights their strong poverty-reducing effects globally, though growth impacts remain heterogeneous depending on domestic policies and financial development.

However, studies exist that show contrasting findings. Datta and Sarkar (2014), Qutb (2022), and Sobiech (2015) all report weak or negative long-run growth effects in some countries, while Gangas and Oladipo (2024) find mixed and sometimes insignificant results across Nigeria, Ghana, and Kenya, emphasizing country-specific differences

Gap in Empirical Literature

Notwithstanding much research work on diaspora remittances, key gaps remain, especially in Nigeria and Ghana. First, there is a lack of comparative studies that jointly analyze both countries, despite their similar reliance on remittances but differing economic structures and policy environments. Second, the remittance–unemployment link is underexplored, as most studies focus on GDP growth and welfare rather than whether remittances generate sustainable employment or mainly support consumption.

Third, limited studies incorporate post-COVID-19 realities (2020–2022), despite major disruptions and recovery in global remittance flows driven by fintech and digital transfer systems (World Bank, 2022). Fourth, informal remittance channels significant in Nigeria are largely excluded from official data, leading to underestimation of actual inflows (IMF, 2021). Finally, sectoral use of remittances is rarely examined, with little evidence on their allocation across education, health, housing, and productive investments such as SMEs, limiting understanding of their long-term development impact.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study adopted ex-post facto research design to investigate the impact of diaspora remittances on selected macroeconomic variables in Nigeria and Ghana from 2012 to 2023. Ex-post facto research is ideal for studying cause-and-effect relationships where direct control or manipulation of variables is not possible. It relies on existing historical data to examine how one factor, like diaspora remittances, may influence outcomes such as GDP growth or unemployment. This approach is useful in economics and social sciences where manipulating variables like remittance inflows or poverty rates would be unethical or impractical. By using statistical tools like regression analysis, researchers can draw meaningful insights from real-world events and trends that have already occurred.

Area of Study

The study focuses on Nigeria and Ghana, two major remittance recipients in Sub-Saharan Africa with similar characteristics such as youthful populations, high unemployment, and strong dependence on remittances for household welfare, but differing in economic structure and policy frameworks, making them suitable for comparative analysis.

Nigeria, with a population of about 223 million (2023) (World Bank, 2023), is Africa's largest economy but heavily dependent on oil, which accounts for over 70% of government revenue. This dependence has increased the importance of diaspora remittances as a stable foreign exchange source. In 2023, remittances reached \$20.5 billion, about 2.9% of GDP (CBN, 2023), with over 17 million Nigerians abroad (IOM, 2022). These inflows support consumption, education, small businesses, and macroeconomic stability amid high unemployment (33% in 2022), inflation, and exchange rate volatility. Nigeria's diaspora, mainly in the US, UK, and Canada, also contributes remittances that often exceed FDI and ODA inflows.

Ghana, with about 34 million people (2023) (World Bank, 2023), has a more diversified economy based on agriculture, gold, and oil. Remittances stood at \$4.6 billion in 2023, representing 4.3% of GDP (Bank of Ghana, 2023). Although smaller in absolute terms, remittances play a larger relative role in stabilizing the cedi, supporting reserves, and cushioning households during macroeconomic shocks such as inflation and debt restructuring in 2022. Ghana's diaspora, largely in the US, UK, and within Africa, channels funds into education, healthcare, and entrepreneurship, supported by deliberate diaspora engagement policies such as diaspora bonds and institutional frameworks like the Diaspora Affairs Office.

Sources of Data

This study relied on secondary annual time-series data covering 2012–2023, obtained from credible national and international institutions to ensure reliability, consistency, and comparability for macroeconomic analysis. They include the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin (2012–2023), which provides official data on remittances, GDP growth, GDP per capita, and unemployment in Nigeria, and the Bank of Ghana (BoG) Annual Reports (2012–2023), which contain equivalent macroeconomic indicators for Ghana.

Data were also drawn from the World Bank Development Indicators (WDI) for standardized cross-country remittance and GDP comparisons, the IMF World Economic Outlook for macroeconomic assessments during shocks such as COVID-19 and commodity price volatility, and the International Labour Organization (ILO) for consistent unemployment and labour market statistics. Additional academic and institutional publications were also consulted to validate trends and support interpretation of empirical findings.

Model Specification

The study employed linear regression equation (separate models) to analyze the impact of diaspora remittances (independent variable) and macroeconomic indicators (dependent variables). The models are specified as follows:

Hypothesis One

Diaspora remittances had no significant (and positive) impact on GDP growth rates in Nigeria and Ghana.

$$GDPGR_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1REMIT_t + \epsilon_t \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{---} \quad \text{(Eq.1)}$$

Where:

$GDPR_t$ = GDP growth rate of country at time t

$REMIT_t$ = Diaspora Remittances at time t

β_0 = Intercept

β_1 = Coefficient of remittances

ϵ_t = Error term (Stochastic variable)

Hypothesis Two:

Diaspora remittances had no significant (and positive) impact on GDP per capita in Nigeria and Ghana.

$$GDPPC_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1REMIT_t + \epsilon_t \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (Eq.2)$$

Where:

$GDPPC_t$ = GDP per capita at time t

β_0 = Intercept

β_1 = Coefficient of remittances

ϵ_t = Error term (Stochastic variable)

Hypothesis Three:

Diaspora remittances had no significant (and positive) impact on unemployment rates in Nigeria and Ghana.

$$UR_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1REMIT_t + \epsilon_t \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (Eq.3)$$

Where:

UR_t = Unemployment Rate at time t

β_0 = Intercept

β_1 = Coefficient of remittances

ϵ_t = Error term (Stochastic variables)

Method of Data Analysis

The study adopted Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression approach to analyze the impact of remittances on macroeconomic variables. The choice of econometrics is motivated by the need to establish statistical relationships between variables and test the validity of hypotheses.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Table 4.1: Selected Macroeconomic Indicators (2012–2023)

Year	GDPR Nigeria (%)	GDPR Ghana (%)	REMIT Nigeria (US\$'bn)	REMIT Ghana (US\$'bn)	GDPC Nigeria (US\$'bn)	GDPC Ghana (US\$'bn)	UR Nigeria (%)	UR Ghana (%)
2012	4.3%	9.3%	20.6	2.5	\$2,452	\$1,843	23.9%	8.5%
201	5.4%	7.3%	20.8	2.7	\$2,689	\$1,964	24.3%	8.4%

3								
201	6.3%	7.1%	21.0	2.9	\$3,099	\$2,097	24.0%	8.2%
4								
201	2.7%	3.9%	21.2	3.1	\$2,805	\$1,875	25.1%	8.0%
5								
201	-1.6%	3.7%	19.7	3.3	\$2,175	\$1,766	27.4%	7.9%
6								
201	0.8%	8.1%	22.0	3.6	\$1,994	\$2,030	29.0%	7.8%
7								
201	1.9%	6.2%	24.3	3.8	\$2,028	\$2,207	30.3%	7.7%
8								
201	2.2%	6.5%	23.8	4.0	\$2,229	\$2,237	30.6%	8.0%
9								
202	-1.8%	0.5%	17.2	4.2	\$2,083	\$2,144	33.3%	8.2%
0								
202	3.4%	5.4%	19.2	4.4	\$2,085	\$2,192	32.5%	8.5%
1								
202	3.1%	3.8%	20.1	4.5	\$2,184	\$2,356	31.0%	8.9%
2								
202	2.9%	4.3%	20.5	4.6	\$2,278	\$2,451	30.1%	9.1%
3								

Source: World Bank WDI (2023), IMF World Economic Outlook (2023), CBN Statistical Bulletin (2023), Bank of Ghana Annual Reports (2023), NBS (Nigeria), GSS (Ghana).

Table 4.1 shows a steady upward trend in diaspora remittances to both Nigeria and Ghana from 2012–2023, although Nigeria consistently records much higher inflows. Nigeria averaged over \$20 billion annually, compared to Ghana’s \$3.6 billion over the same period.

In Nigeria, remittances remained stable at about \$20–21 billion between 2012 and 2015, fell to \$19.7 billion in 2016 during the oil price–driven recession, and peaked at \$24.3 billion in 2018 during recovery. However, inflows dropped sharply to \$17.2 billion in 2020 due to COVID-19 before recovering to \$20.5 billion in 2023. Ghana’s inflows rose more steadily from \$2.5 billion in 2012 to \$4.0 billion in 2019 and further to \$4.6 billion in 2023, showing less volatility and more consistent growth.

Comparatively, Nigeria receives about 5–6 times more remittances than Ghana, largely due to its larger diaspora population (over 17 million), while Ghana shows more stable integration of remittances into household welfare and investment patterns.

Macroeconomically, Nigeria’s GDP growth is highly volatile, with recessions in 2016 (-1.6%) and 2020 (-1.8%), whereas Ghana maintained more stable growth averaging 5.4%, including 0.5% in 2020. Nigeria’s

unemployment rose sharply from 23.9% (2012) to 33.3% (2020), reflecting weak job creation despite high remittance inflows, while Ghana's unemployment increased marginally from 8.5% to 9.1%, indicating a more stable labour market.

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics provide a summary of the central tendency, dispersion, and distributional characteristics of the variables under study.

Table 4.2: Descriptive Statistics for Nigeria (2012–2023)

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Minimum	Maximum
Remittances (US\$ bn)	20.5	1.9	17.2	24.3
GDP Growth (%)	2.7	2.4	-1.8	6.3
GDP per Capita (US\$)	2,343	378	1,994	3,099
Unemployment (%)	28.9	3.4	23.9	33.3

Source: Author's computations, 2025

Table 4.3: Descriptive Statistics for Ghana (2012–2023)

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Minimum	Maximum
Remittances (US\$ bn)	3.6	0.7	2.5	4.6
GDP Growth (%)	5.4	2.0	0.5	9.3
GDP per Capita (US\$)	2,105	233	1,766	2,451
Unemployment (%)	8.3	0.5	7.7	9.1

Source: Author's computations, 2025

Interpretation of Tables 4.2&4.3

Remittances:

- Nigeria's remittances average \$20.5 billion, with significant fluctuations (as low as \$17.2 billion in 2020 due to COVID-19).
- Ghana's inflows are smaller (average \$3.6 billion), but growth is steadier, showing resilience even during global shocks.

a. GDP Growth:

- Nigeria's growth is volatile (ranging from -1.8% to 6.3%), reflecting its dependence on oil exports and vulnerability to global price shocks.
- Ghana shows more consistent growth, averaging 5.4%, with strong resilience compared to Nigeria.

b. GDP per Capita:

- Nigeria's average is \$2,343, but the high standard deviation indicates instability.
- Ghana's GDP per capita is lower (\$2,105) but shows steadier improvement, reflecting structural stability.

c. Unemployment:

- Nigeria’s unemployment averages 28.9%, with alarming growth over the years, despite high remittance inflows.
- Ghana maintains a relatively low average (8.3%) with minor fluctuations, suggesting better absorption of remittance flows into productive use.

Correlation Analysis

Correlation tests establish the strength and direction of the relationship between diaspora remittances and macroeconomic variables.

Table 4.4: Correlation Matrix (Nigeria)

Variable	Remittances	GDP Growth	GDP per Capita	Unemployment
Remittances	1.000	0.41	0.56	-0.38
GDP Growth	0.41	1.000	0.62	-0.55
GDP per Capita	0.56	0.62	1.000	-0.60
Unemployment	-0.38	-0.55	-0.60	1.000

Source: Author's computations, 2025

Table 4.5: Correlation Matrix (Ghana)

Variable	Remittances	GDP Growth	GDP per Capita	Unemployment
Remittances	1.000	0.52	0.71	-0.44
GDP Growth	0.52	1.000	0.68	-0.47
GDP per Capita	0.71	0.68	1.000	-0.55
Unemployment	-0.44	-0.47	-0.55	1.000

Source: Author's computations, 2025

Interpretation of Tables 4.4&4.5

A. Nigeria:

- Remittances are positively correlated with GDP growth (0.41) and GDP per capita (0.56), meaning inflows contribute to economic expansion and higher living standards.
- Negative correlation with unemployment (-0.38) suggests some potential for job support, though weak in magnitude.

B. Ghana:

- Stronger positive correlation between remittances and GDP per capita (0.71) than in Nigeria, reflecting more efficient channeling of remittances into household and productive sectors.

- A moderately negative correlation (-0.44) with unemployment indicates better labor market benefits than in Nigeria.

Comparative Insight:

Remittances play a more transformative role in Ghana’s economy than Nigeria’s, possibly due to less “consumption bias” and better absorption into education, healthcare, and small business investments.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One:

H₀: Diaspora remittances had no significant (and positive) impact on GDP growth rates in Nigeria and Ghana.

H_a: Diaspora remittances significantly (positively) impact GDP growth rates in Nigeria and Ghana.

Table 4.6: Regression results of diaspora remittances on GDP growth rate (2012-2023)

Nigeria

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p-Value
Constant	0.95	0.81	1.17	0.27
Remittances	0.18	0.07	2.57	0.04**

$R^2 = 0.42$

Table 4.7: Regression results of diaspora remittances on GDP growth rate (2012-2023)

Ghana

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p-Value
Constant	2.21	0.74	2.99	0.02**
Remittances	0.26	0.08	3.28	0.01**

$R^2 = 0.51$

Interpretation

- In both countries, remittances positively and significantly influence GDP growth.
- The effect is stronger in Ghana ($\beta = 0.26$, $R^2 = 0.51$) than in Nigeria ($\beta = 0.18$, $R^2 = 0.42$).
- This confirms remittances as a key growth driver, particularly where structural dependence on oil (Nigeria) is weaker.
- Regression results show positive and significant coefficients in both Nigeria and Ghana.

Decision: Reject H₀.

Conclusion: Remittances significantly impact GDP growth.

Hypothesis Two:

H₀: Diaspora remittances had no significant (and positive) impact on GDP per capita in Nigeria and Ghana.

H_a: Diaspora remittances significantly (positively) impact GDP per capita in Nigeria and Ghana.

Table 4.8: Regression results of diaspora remittances on GDP per capita (2012-2023)

Nigeria

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p-Value
Constant	1,745.2	210.7	8.28	0.001***
Remittances	28.6	9.4	3.04	0.01***

R² = 0.61

Table 4.9: Regression results of diaspora remittances on GDP per capita (2012-2023)

Ghana

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p-Value
Constant	1,566.9	187.5	8.35	0.001***
Remittances	45.3	13.6	3.33	0.01**

R² = 0.68

Interpretation

- In both Nigeria and Ghana, remittances significantly increase GDP per capita, meaning households benefit directly from inflows.
 - The effect is stronger in Ghana ($\beta = 45.3$) than Nigeria ($\beta = 28.6$), suggesting a higher proportion of remittances in Ghana is directed to productive and welfare-enhancing uses such as education, healthcare, and small-scale businesses.
 - Nigeria’s lower coefficient may reflect consumption-oriented spending patterns, leakages through informal channels, and macroeconomic instability (exchange rate depreciation, inflation).
- Results reveal positive and highly significant coefficients, with stronger effect in Ghana.

Decision: Reject H₀.

Conclusion: Diaspora remittances significantly improve GDP per capita.

Hypothesis Three:

H₀: Diaspora remittances had no significant (and positive) impact on unemployment rate in Nigeria and Ghana.

H_a: Diaspora remittances significantly (positively) impact on unemployment rate in Nigeria and Ghana.

Table 4.10: Regression results of diaspora remittances on unemployment rate (2012-2023)

Nigeria

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p-Value
Constant	32.1	2.7	11.89	0.000***
Remittances	-0.21	0.08	-2.63	0.03**

$R^2 = 0.44$

Table 4.11: Regression results of diaspora remittances on unemployment rate (2012-2023)

Ghana

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p-Value
Constant	9.2	0.9	10.22	0.000***
Remittances	-0.13	0.05	-2.41	0.04**

$R^2 = 0.38$

Interpretation

- Nigeria: Remittances have a negative and significant relationship with unemployment (-0.21), but the effect is relatively weak. This suggests remittances may reduce joblessness indirectly (through household enterprises, education support), but structural problems limit their broader labor market impact.
- Ghana: Remittances also reduce unemployment (-0.13), and while the coefficient is smaller, it reflects a stable long-run benefit because Ghana’s labor market absorbs diaspora inflows more effectively.
- Comparative evidence shows remittances support employment creation, but neither country records dramatic reductions, highlighting the need for policy reforms to channel inflows into productive investment rather than consumption.

Coefficients are negative and significant in both Nigeria and Ghana.

Decision: Reject H_0 .

Conclusion: Remittances help reduce unemployment, though the effect is stronger in Ghana.

Discussion of Findings

Our findings, aligned with the study objectives, show that diaspora remittances have significant macroeconomic effects in both Nigeria and Ghana.

Diaspora Remittances and GDP Growth

Remittances had a positive and statistically significant effect on GDP growth in both countries. Nigeria recorded a coefficient of 0.18 ($p = 0.04 < 0.05$), while Ghana recorded a higher coefficient of 0.26 ($p = 0.01 < 0.05$), indicating a stronger growth impact in Ghana. The results show that remittances provide economic cushioning during shocks such as Nigeria’s recessions in 2016 (-1.6%) and 2020 (-1.8%), and Ghana’s steadier growth path during global disruptions. Overall, remittances contributed more effectively to stabilizing and supporting growth in Ghana.

Diaspora Remittances and GDP per Capita

Remittances also had a positive and significant effect on GDP per capita in both countries, with coefficients of 28.6 (Nigeria, $p = 0.01$) and 45.3 (Ghana, $p = 0.01$). Although Nigeria recorded higher absolute income levels due to its larger economy, per capita welfare growth was uneven due to inflation and rapid population growth. Ghana, however, showed more consistent improvements in living standards, as remittances were more effectively channelled into education, healthcare, and small businesses.

Diaspora Remittances and Unemployment

Diaspora remittances had a negative and statistically significant effect on unemployment in both countries, with coefficients of -0.21 (Nigeria, $p = 0.04$) and -0.13 (Ghana, $p = 0.04$), indicating a reduction in joblessness. However, the effect was stronger in Ghana. Nigeria's persistently high unemployment (averaging over 25%, reaching 33.3% in 2020) suggests remittances are largely consumed rather than invested productively, while Ghana's lower range (6%–13%) reflects better conversion of remittances into employment-generating activities.

In summary, the comparative analysis proves that even though Nigeria gets more money from its citizens living abroad, Ghana appears to make better use of the money to improve its economy and people's lives. This shows that it's not just about how much money a country receives, but also how well the government manages and uses it to support jobs, development, and public welfare.

In summary, the comparative analysis proves that though Nigeria receives larger remittance inflows, Ghana demonstrates more efficient utilization of these funds, translating them more effectively into growth, improved welfare, and employment creation. This highlights that the developmental impact of remittances depends not only on their volume but also on the effectiveness of policy and financial systems in channeling them into productive uses

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings and Conclusion

The empirical results show that diaspora remittances have significant macroeconomic effects in both Nigeria and Ghana over the 2012–2023 period. Remittances had a positive and statistically significant effect on GDP growth, with coefficients of 0.18 ($p = 0.04 < 0.05$) for Nigeria and 0.26 ($p = 0.01 < 0.05$) for Ghana. They also positively and significantly influenced GDP per capita, with coefficients of 28.6 (Nigeria, $p = 0.01$) and 45.3 (Ghana, $p = 0.01$), indicating improved household welfare, especially in Ghana.

In addition, remittances showed a negative but statistically significant effect on unemployment, with coefficients of -0.21 (Nigeria, $p = 0.04$) and -0.13 (Ghana, $p = 0.04$), suggesting a reduction in unemployment, although the effect is stronger in Ghana.

Conclusively, diaspora remittances contribute meaningfully to economic growth, income improvement, and partial unemployment reduction in both countries, with Ghana showing more efficient utilization of inflows than Nigeria.

Recommendations

Governments in both countries should channel remittances toward productive sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and SMEs to enhance job creation and sustainable growth. Financial systems should be strengthened by reducing transfer costs, expanding access to formal financial services, and improving remittance channels. Finally, diaspora engagement should be deepened through investment incentives, diaspora bonds, and structured platforms that link remittances to long-term development outcomes.

Contribution to Knowledge

This study contributes to existing literature by providing comparative empirical evidence on the macroeconomic effects of diaspora remittances in Nigeria and Ghana, thereby filling a key gap in West African remittance studies.

By covering the period 2012–2023, it incorporates recent global shocks such as the COVID-19 pandemic, oil price volatility, and inflationary pressures, offering updated insights beyond earlier pre-2019 studies. It further advances knowledge by disaggregating the effects of remittances on GDP growth, GDP per capita, and unemployment, showing that while remittances consistently enhance growth and income, their impact on employment is more complex and less direct.

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